

English proverbs and their usage
International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan
E-mail: zizerion@mail.ru

Senior Teacher, Abushaev Amir, +99890 922 25 83

Abstract

Proverbs are popularly defined as short expressions of popular wisdom. Efforts to improve on the popular definition have not led to a more precise definition. The wisdom is in the form of a general observation about the world or a bit of advice, sometimes more nearly an attitude toward a situation. Irrespective of what field or profession one works in, the use of English is very important these days. Communication using English has become pertinent for all professionals in every formal sector. This is why we need to ensure that our command over the language is clear. Apart from ensuring that our grammar is perfect, we must also focus on using tools to enrich our communication. For example, we can use proverbs to explain ideas better.

Key words: main, real, vital, significance, priority, visible, reality, internal, international, spectators, global, decision, specific, obvious, example

Международная Исламская Академия Узбекистана

E-mail: zizerion@mail.ru

+99890 9222583

Отрывок

Английский язык используется в качестве родного примерно для 400 миллионов человек во многих странах мира. Таким образом, английский является третьим по распространенности языком после китайского и испанского. Поэтому участие в таких экзаменах, как IELTS, во всем мире довольно велико. Официального определения «глобального» или «мирового» языка не существует, но, по сути, он относится к языку, который изучается и на котором говорят на международном уровне, и характеризуется не только количеством носителей его родного и второго языков, но и географическим расположением. распространение и его использование в международных организациях и в дипломатических отношениях. Глобальный язык действует как «лингва франка», общий язык, который позволяет людям разного

происхождения и национальностей общаться на более или менее равноправной основе.

Ключевые слова: главный, реальный, жизненно важный, значимость, приоритет, видимый, реальность, внутренний, международный, зрители, глобальный, решение, конкретный, очевидный, пример

that are particular to a certain country. They are short, wise sayings that usually offer some kind of advice, or capture an idea found in life.

Native English speakers frequently use proverbs in their conversations, and they often do this without even realizing it. Proverbs sometimes reveal more about the culture of a country than any textbook can. The values of the population are reflected in its proverbs.

Proverbs are also a critical part of engaging fluently with people of a particular culture. Ask any English tutor from the UK what some common English proverbs are, and they are sure to be different from those of an English tutor from the USA.

That's why we put together this guide of the 30 most popular proverbs in English, so you can know them when you see them (and maybe dish a few of your own).

For more direct help from English tutors, take English lessons online with Preply.

30 Most popular proverbs in English for students & learners

There are probably a thousand proverbs out there, so we curated this list of the most popular need-to-know proverbs in English.

1. Many hands make light work

When many people work together to accomplish a difficult task, it doesn't seem so difficult. That is the general meaning of this English proverb. In other words, if people work together, the work is easier and is completed more quickly.

2. Strike while the iron is hot

This proverb means that you should take advantage of a favorable situation before it changes.

3. Honesty is the best policy

It is best to always be honest and tell the truth. By doing so, you will win the trust and respect of others.

4. The grass is always greener on the other side of the fence

Other people's lives always seem better, happier, and more successful than yours, even if your life is going well.

5. Don't judge a book by its cover

Don't form an opinion or make a judgment about someone or something based on its outward appearance.

6. An apple a day keeps the doctor away

Proverbs and sayings are popular nuggets of wisdom, often in circulation for centuries and even millenniums. This post covers more than 200 common proverbs, each of which is followed by meaning and use in an example sentence.

If you're looking for more proverbs and sayings, you can find plenty of them in the resource below. It contains proverbs on topics such as life, family, friends, love, health, happiness, money, hard work, time, time management, teamwork, leadership, business, education & learning, and more.

Resource on proverbs and sayings

1. A bad workman always blames his tools.

This proverb is used when someone blames the quality of their equipment or other external factors when they perform a task poorly.

Example: X: The food isn't cooked well because the oven is not functioning well. Y: Well, it's the case of a bad workman blaming his tools.

2. A bird in hand is worth two in the bush.

Certainty of having something in hand is better than mere probability of having even more things.

Example: X: Why did you turn down that job offer when you don't have anything concrete in hand at the moment? Y: Well, I'm confident I'll land one of the two jobs I interviewed for last week. And they're better than this one. X: In my opinion, you should've taken it. A bird in hand is worth two in the bush.

3. Absence makes heart grow fonder.

When we're away from loved ones, we long for their company more than in normal times.

Example: When I was with him, he always fought with me, but now he cries for me on phone. I think distance made his heart grow fonder.

4. A cat has nine lives.

Cat can survive seemingly fatal events.

Example: I haven't seen him in months, but I wouldn't really worry about him. Everyone knows a cat has nine lives.

5. Action speaks louder than words.

Action is a better reflection of one's character than words because it's easy to say things, but difficult to act on them and follow through.

Example: The interviewee had an impressive resume, but he struggled to perform the task given during the interview. Actions speak louder than words, don't they?

6. A diamond with a flaw is better than a common stone that is perfect.

A rare, precious opportunity that comes with some problems is better than a regular opportunity that seems to be perfect.

Example: I would advise you to work in a market that is growing fast than in a mature market. The former has its own problems, but that's where you grow fast in your career. A diamond with a flaw is better than a common stone that is perfect.

7. A drowning man will clutch a straw.

When someone is in a difficult situation, s/he will take any available opportunity to come out of it.

Example: After trying all reliable medicines, he is now visiting quacks to get a cure for his baldness. A drowning man will clutch a straw.

A stitch in time, saves nine. Have you ever heard this advice in the context of asking you to act in time to avoid issues later? Or have you ever been told

not to judge a book by its cover, warning you that appearances may be deceptive? These pieces of advice came to you by way of commonly used English proverbs.

The dictionary defines a proverb as “a short, well-known pithy saying, stating a general truth or piece of advice.” These are brief, memorable sayings that tend to stay with you. In fact, you can look at them as shared lessons of life that find a connection across cultures and generations. They have a way of tapping into the human experience at large.

Table of Contents

Is there a difference between proverbs and idioms?

1. Strike while the iron is hot
2. Absence Makes the Heart Grow Fonder
3. A Bird in Hand is Worth Two in the Bush
4. Grass is greener on the other side
5. Rome wasn't built in a day
6. Don't bite off more than you can chew
7. Don't make a mountain out of a molehill
8. Where there is a will, there is a way
9. A rolling stone gathers no moss
10. When in Rome, do as the Romans do
11. Birds of a feather flock together
12. Those in glass houses ought not to throw stones at others
13. Learn to walk before you run
14. The early bird catches the worm
15. Beauty lies in the eyes of the beholder

To Sum Up

Is there a difference between proverbs and idioms?

Simply put, an idiom is a commonly used phrase that has a specific meaning that may not be understood from the meaning of its individual words. Let us take the idiom “to rub someone the wrong way”, which means to annoy someone. The meaning of this idiom will not be clear from its constituent words and you are likely to understand the meaning if you have heard the idiom before.

A proverb, on the other hand, as we discussed earlier, refers to a short and popular saying that offers well meaning advice. In terms of the literal meaning of a proverb, it is far clearer than an idiom, although the intended meanings of several proverbs may not be their literal meanings. Let us try to understand it with an example- in the proverb “Do not cry over spilt milk”, the actual reference isn’t to milk at all. However by making a reference to “spilt milk”, a reference is being made to something gone wrong, as it were.

References

1. Maceachen, D. B. (1950) ‘Wilkie Collins and British law’, *Nineteenth-Century Fiction*, 5(2), pp. 121–139.
2. Bosch, H. (1482) *The last judgement [Triptych]*. Groeningemuseum, Bruges.
3. Stapleton, P. B. (2017). *EFT for Teens*. Hay House.
4. Taylor, A. (2017). *Troubled everyday: The aesthetics of violence and the everyday in European art cinema*. Edinburgh University Press.
5. Watt, B. D., O’Leary, J., & O’Toole, S. (2017). Juvenile fitness for trial: Lawyer and youth justice officer professional survey. *Psychiatry, Psychology and Law*, 24(2), 191–204. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13218719.2016.1220036>
6. Bolton, G. C. (Speaker). (1975). *Towards an Australian environmental history [Speech audio recording]*. Media Services, Murdoch University.
7. Bond, L., Carlin, J. B., Thomas, L., Rubin, K., & Patton, G. (2001). Does bullying cause emotional problems? A prospective study of young teenagers. *BMJ*, 323, 480-484. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.323.7311.480>
8. Borman, W. C., Hanson, M. A., Oppler, S. H., Pulakos, E. D., & White, L. A. (1993). Role of early supervisory experience in supervisor performance.

Journal of Applied Psychology, 78, 443-449. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.78.3.443>

9. Colclough, B., & Colclough, J. (1999). A challenge to change. Thorsons.

10. Delalande, J. (2019, October 26). Our teens struggle the most. The West Australian, p. 32. Factiva. https://global-factiva-com.libproxy.murdoch.edu.au/ha/default.aspx#./!/?&_suid=1576141953014019681669927131606

11. Department of Health and Aged Care. (1999). Mental health: A report focusing on depression, 1998. Commonwealth of Australia.

12. Department of Health and Aged Care. (2000). National youth suicide prevention strategy. Australian Government. <http://www.health.gov.au/hsdd/mentalhe/sp/nysps/about.htm>